

NOSTALGIA PLUS MEMORY: VERSATILE BUBBLE TEA SCARVES

Chia-Yu Wu, [†]Chia-Hung Hsu

Eclat Textile Co., Ltd, Taiwan, ^{*}De Montfort University
clairewu8@gmail.com, domustt@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

When being overseas and experiencing different cultures, a longing for home and the familiar may creep into daily life. International students in particular may feel homesick in the unfamiliar country, reducing an individual's confidence in their new surroundings. To address this, theories were explored and research conducted with the aim of creating a collection of scarves which celebrate the national identity of Taiwanese female students and evoke particular memories of family in the homeland. The research findings ascertained that handmade crafts are appealing to Taiwanese female customers, with protection from the cold and decorative features as the main elements of interest to the target market. A design concept was developed around an immediately recognisable beverage to Taiwanese: the Taiwanese bubble tea drink, representing itself as a symbol of national identity. Regarding emotional aspects, family is the key point related to homesickness. This product may enhance the Taiwanese wearer's identity, bring a degree of comfort from home, and remind target audiences of Taiwan. When given as a gift by family, the item may further carry those associations from home and family. Therefore, bubble tea handmade scarves can be seen as cultural products with physical and psychological functions with the hope of delivering the essence of Taiwan via a well-known Taiwanese beverage.

Keywords: nostalgia, national identity, overseas student, scarf, bubble tea.

INTRODUCTION

As a textile designer, business trips in the past have induced feelings of homesickness, which when

coupled with large expenditures of energy and effort could bring about fatigue. Similarly, in becoming an international student, the signs of stress from living in another place within an alien culture appeared unconsciously. It takes time to become familiar with and adjust to different kinds of food, weather and culture when people inhabit a new environment. However, certain items can remind travellers of their home and country and arouse a degree of nostalgia while they become accustomed to their new surroundings.

The background to the research is derived from the following considerations. First of all, travel in general is on the rise. In the UK, air travel represented 60% of all trips taken abroad in 1981, climbing to 81% in 2005. The proportion of travel to the UK by overseas residents also rose with 30 million visitors in 2005, compared to 11.5 million visitors in 1981 (Social Trends 2007:168). Secondly, foreign travel helps people broaden their horizons. It may also, however, bring about stress and fatigue (Vivian Wu Organisation n.d.). Inevitably, each overseas student grows up in an environment which differs in a variety of ways from the one they are visiting. Attachment to object and place may develop in early stages. Accordingly, developing a product for certain travellers that can deliver familiar images or concepts from their home country may be of particular value. Hence, this study, referring to personal experiences, containing relevant theories, investigations and statistics analysis aims to create a collection of bubble tea scarves for female Taiwanese students abroad to relieve homesickness and enhance the sense of national identity.

METHODOLOGY

Figure 1. The flowchart of the research

The methodology (Figure 1) contains six integral stages. First of all, investigation of psychological theories such as nostalgia, attachment to place or objects, national identity and handicrafts are carried out at the secondary research level to understand the relationship among mental health, identity and handmade products and accumulate design inspirations.

Afterwards, primary research including observation, interviews and questionnaires aimed to unveil particular aspects which cannot be discovered in the literature review. Observation and interviews carried out would provide insights into the target market's scarf preferences and attachment to particular items so as to develop rationales. This observation used a pool of ten Taiwanese female overseas students in order to collect a range of information relevant to scarf design, including patterns and scarf construction. Participants' rooms were examined to find if there were any particular items such as photos or soft toys around the target user of personal emotional significance. If yes, understanding the anecdotal evidence related to these items was necessary. On the other hand, if there were no such items in view, participants were asked whether they brought objects like this when travelling abroad and if so, the story behind the item was explored. At the next stage, interviews with the same ten participants aimed to investigate scarf preferences, and photographs of their favourite scarf were also needed to analyse and

compare scarf patterns and textures. Based on analysis, questions for the questionnaire were generated, and quantitative and qualitative measures were utilised containing open and closed questions. Thirty-one female Taiwanese overseas students with an easygoing character trait were recruited, and questionnaires were sent through social network media and emails. Collection took a fortnight, and methods closed with statistical analysis from which the design rationales were developed.

After the secondary and primary research into the target market and their preferences, further literature review was undertaken to determine materials and realise features of Taiwanese bubble tea in order to proceed with prototype scarf designs. Design and Development included two steps: testing work evaluation and final designs. Presenting testing work to a focus group was to gain recommendations. Then final designs based on the feedback attained were undertaken.

After this, interviews for design evaluation were arranged which examined the product in terms of scarf design and psychological aspects. Lastly, significant findings related to emotional, cultural and marketing aspects were unveiled and are described in the discussion section.

INVESTIGATION OF NOSTALGIA, NATIONAL IDENTITY AND BUBBLE TEA

NOSTALGIA

A considerable amount of literature has been published on nostalgia but its definition varies. For instance, Swiss physician Johannes Hofer initially coined the term in the late 17th century referring to "the extreme homesickness that Swiss mercenaries experienced (Wilson 2005:22)." It was a psychological disease, however, nostalgia is considered as an emotion that combines "bitterness and sweetness, [...] the new and the familiar, absence and presence (Harper 1966)". Nostalgia changes one's attitude and emotion "to produce comfort and security (Wilson 2005:23)". As time goes by, the negative nostalgia has been dissolved, and various nostalgia products appeared such as when Coca-Cola brought back the glass bottle, and when the packaging of Johnson &

Johnson was replaced with the 1950s formula design. Similarly, old typeface were used by Maxwell House (Taylor 1995:16). They attempt to arouse feelings of ‘the good old days’.

Harper provides an appropriate description of nostalgia. Nostalgia is indeed an emotion mingling with complicated and intangible items and may represent the emotions in an international student’s state of mind, the longing for a sense of warmth and the familiar they would like to gain and yet is difficult to achieve far away from home.

NATIONAL IDENTITY

The concept of a nation has been defined from different point of views. Benedict Anderson (1983:7) contends that a nation can be considered as an ‘imagined community’. His idea concentrates on the fact that nationhood is reproduced and imagined, and he attempts to ‘efface the spatial, material and embodied production of communal identities (Edensor 2002:7)’. Nevertheless, Anthony Smith’s theory (1998:187) contrasts with Anderson’s idea and asserts that nations are formed from ethnic communities. Based on the symbol of ethnic group, people can distinguish the difference. Moreover, people with the same memories, history and heritage can differentiate themselves from others.

Undoubtedly, history for a nation is essential; however, everyday things serve to distinguish nation to nation. Edensor (2002: 9) contends that history is overstressed and cannot account for national identity which is dynamic and ambiguous. Instead, he puts emphasis on everyday life such as routine, habits and food. Daily events do not change much and each nation ‘owns’ the character of its everyday life, revealing differences between various nations (Edensor 2002: 19). Therefore, one finds symbols of national identity in everyday items and events, and not exclusively by reaching back into a nation’s historical past.

BUBBLE TEA

Bubble tea is very common beverage in Taiwan and may be found in approximately 8,000 bubble tea cafés throughout the country. (Kingsley 2011). It is a sugary drink invented by an enterprising market trader in the

1980s who created an experimental new beverage by mixing tapioca, ice and normal tea (Kingsley 2011). According to the website of Bubbleology (n.d.), which announced that they sell authentic Taiwanese bubble tea in London’s Soho, the origins of the name ‘come from small floating bubbles created by the vigorous shaking involved in making bubble tea’. Referring to Figure 2, the features of bubble tea are as follows.

Firstly, normal tea is mixed with cream, producing a milky tea colour. Then there are plenty of bubbles on top due to vigorous shaking. On the bottom of the glass are black, sweet and chewy tapioca balls (Figure 3). In order to enjoy tea and tapioca balls at the same time, extra wide straws are required. With these special features, bubble tea is therefore a highly recognisable beverage.

Figure 2. Chun Shui Tang’s (Taiwanese tea café) best seller, bubble milk tea

Figure 3. Tapioca balls

The unique beverage is popular among Taiwanese overseas students. According to Assad Khan, founder of London’s Bubbleology, the main customers are mostly Taiwanese tourists and overseas students (Zhong 2011). It seems that Taiwanese travellers may ease their homesickness by having a cup of bubble tea. For Taiwanese travellers, seeing this beverage

which is ubiquitous in Taiwan, appear in other countries lends a feeling of familiarity. Bubble tea denotes a well-known Taiwanese beverage and has become a recognisable symbol of the nation's identity rooted in Taiwanese people's mind. Thus it can be taken into consideration as an inspiration when proceeding with the design work.

ATTACHMENT TO OBJECTS SCARF PREFERENCES

Completing the observation and interviews, there was statistical analysis indicating target customers' attachment to certain items. Firstly, Taiwanese female overseas students had a tendency towards attachment to certain objects, specifically, soft toys. According to the results of the observation, six out of ten participants were attached to particular objects. The items varied, and included photos, music and soft toys to which three in six participants were attached. Secondly, the objects target users attached to might remind them of family or home. In fact, two participants attaching to soft toys had indicated that the soft toy evoked memories of family in Taiwan. This finding was in agreement with Holmes' (1993) "attachment hierarchy". Namely, people had alternatives to bring other items as second object of attachment to remedy homesickness when they could not travel with their beloved family or pets. Hence, adopting the texture of soft toy, being supple and soft, the design may provide customers with a similar function as soft toys do.

SCARF PREFERENCES

Functions of a scarf were more important than its thickness based on the response of questionnaire. Questions pertaining to scarf thickness were intended to determine the materials and constructions of the scarf. Nonetheless, according to Figure 4, the main considerations of scarves for the respondents were the temperature consideration (40%) followed by dressing (36%). Few respondents cared about thickness. In addition, a majority of participants' scarves were both basic (solid or simple patterned) and fancy-patterned scarves based on interviews which emphasised the idea of diverse scarves going with different types of clothes. This finding was unexpected and inspired the concept of versatility and reversibility. As for design, simple and fancy patterned revealed on the front and back of the scarf

respectively could be feasible in terms of versatility. When turned inside out, the scarf presents two different identities on each side, which achieves the reversibility.

Figure 4. Respondents' preferences related to thickness of scarf

DESIGN RATIONALES

The preliminary design concept of the research can be formulated and after analysing the second and primary research design rationales were developed.

Technique aspects

- A double weave construction was selected because it could present different patterns on front and back respectively on the textile. One side could arrange simple pattern; fancy pattern could be woven on the other side effecting two identities on one scarf.
- To incorporate the symbol of Taiwanese identity into this product, the recognisable bubble tea, a national beverage with chewy tapioca balls, would be the pivotal in terms of colours and texture design. As a result, both the warp and weft yarns should be in a milky tea colour.
- Based on the notion of bubble tea, a see-through effect structure could be applied to the double cloth so as to present the translucent liquid and subtle tapioca balls in it.

Material criteria

- The use of wool and cotton as materials aims to provide target audiences with supple texture just as soft toys.

FINAL DESIGNS

THE FIRST DESIGN

Composition: wool and cotton

Construction: double weave, leno weave, and plain weave

Figure 5. The first design

THE SECOND DESIGN:

Composition: wool and cotton

Construction: double weave, leno weave and plain weave

Figure 6. The second design

THE THIRD DESIGN:

Composition: wool and cotton

Construction: double weave, leno weave, plain weave and tapestry weave

Figure 7. The third design

EVALUATION

The final design evaluation helped the author collect feedback from the focus group. Five interviewees from the earlier stages of primary research were organized into a focus group for this evaluation to help determine whether the product could achieve the aim of the study. In the evaluation, three images were shown to the group, illustrating the length of the scarf and its materials while displaying the product's integrity (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Informing the target group of material and the length of the scarf

This evaluation unveiled several important issues. Four out of five interviewees preferred the first design; they also expressed a preference for soft texture. Only one interviewee considered the third scarf design to be their favourite due to its uniqueness of construction. Contrary to expectations, the second design was not preferred by the focus group though they felt that this design most directly conveyed the notion of a bubble tea beverage. One interviewee points out the reason: the black-coloured balls stand out too much. Another preferred the scattering of wool balls in different sizes. As a result, it was not only presenting features of bubble tea but also injecting other factors into the new design that were crucial.

The logo sewn at the corner of the scarf with its bubble tea graphic helped convey the design concept of the scarf, reminding members of the focus group of Taiwan (80%). A majority of the group felt that this design successfully delivers on the notion of Taiwanese identity (60%). Furthermore, the scarf may be taken by wearers abroad to present their national identity. Two in five commented that they would bring this scarf along when travelling overseas and introduce the characteristic beverage to people unfamiliar with Taiwanese culture. With regard to homesickness, family plays a crucial role in enhancing the function of the scarf, and four out of five interviewees felt the product could help alleviate homesickness only if scarves are given as a gift by family. An additional approach may be that the scarf is provided by family during childhood, allowing deeper associations to form. The target users may then become attached to the article early on, and through the deep psychological bond of family and early memories, resonate with the user throughout a life.

DISCUSSION

Conducting this study advanced the author's design ability and knowledge. A detailed description of key aspects will be given as a reflection upon the study.

To begin with, researching articles pertaining to certain emotional aspects of design posed a challenge. A vast body of literature on themes of national identity exists, however, by comparison, the number of articles addressing emotions in design specifically exploring nostalgia and homesickness is relatively limited. This, to some extent, complicated efforts at the secondary research level. Perhaps people were born in a different family with various cultures or prior knowledge, which may influence their emotions and attitudes; as a result, it is not easy to assess feelings. Moreover, the target market is Taiwanese female overseas students, a niche market more difficult to accumulate relevant information on. Furthermore, the nature of attachment to objects or figures is also related to people's background, habits and privacy. According to the primary research, the significant items of emotional attachment for each respondent vary. Hence, investigating the nature of attachment was also a struggle. These unexpected obstacles could not be avoided, and it took time to accumulate relevant information to finish this study.

A collection of handmade textiles symbolising Taiwanese identity can have other implications and possibilities. It is an accessory imbued with specific cultural notions and a national identity. In terms of distribution, the product can be sold at museum shops, gift shops and virtual shops. As an item with cultural references, visitors from different countries might purchase the scarf as a souvenir in museum shops and gift shops, becoming a channel to promote the product to other nationalities. Moreover, both the beverage and the scarf present common

characteristics, providing opportunities for cross-industry cooperation which may attract both different nationalities and overseas students. According to feedback from the evaluation, when associated with family and given by family members as a gift, the product may alleviate feelings of homesickness to a degree, reinforcing a connection to family and Taiwan. Thus, the bubble tea scarves presented in this context can be both a cultural product and assist in providing other unique benefits relevant to the target market.

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